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Analysis of the Maxim of Relativity in a Patient with Down Syndrome

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ABSTRACT

In this psycholinguistic case study, Miss Fatima, a young woman with Down syndrome, is examined for her conversational adherence to Grice's Maxim of Relevance. This study examines if Miss Fatima violates this maxim, how frequently it occurs, whether she is aware of irrelevant responses, and whether there is any discomfort involved. It does this by focusing on a transcribed interview. Miss Fatima, who was born in 1999, has previously received educational support and speech treatment. In order to comprehend how language, cognitive function, and emotional state interact in people with Down syndrome, this study looks into her conversational habits. The study questions investigate Miss Fatima's emotional response, her awareness of her irrelevant reactions, and the prevalence and proportion of maxim flouting. Miss Fatima's knowledge and comfort levels will be examined, as well as incidents of flouting and their regularity. This study is important because it sheds light on the communication styles and cognitive processes of people with Down syndrome, which could help guide family communication and speech treatment techniques. The study's limitations include its reliance on translated data, single-case design, and possible observational impact on Miss Fatima's behavior. The findings show that Miss Fatima disregarded the relevance principle in nine of the sixteen interview questions, frequently while answering more difficult ones. Her answers point to a combination of cognitive processing issues, conciseness, and possible reluctance during the interview, even if she showed some knowledge of importance.

Keywords: Psycholinguistics, Down Syndrome, Flouting Maxims.

1. INTRODUCTION

Analysis of Maxim of Relativity in patient with Down syndrome comes under Psycho-linguistics. It is a branch of applied linguistics that deals with the application of linguistic knowledge and methods to psychology and cognitive processes. The study of the mental processes behind language production, comprehension, and acquisition is known as psycholinguistics. It investigates how humans comprehend, create, and acquire language (Alduais et al., 2022). The research that is carried out is done with the help of our prestigious patient. In order to maintain the secrecy of patient, she is referred to Miss Fatima as this case study. It is important to note that the following study is done on behalf of Miss Fatima's and her Mother's consent and permission. Miss Fatima was born with Down syndrome in 1999. Since her main concern regarding the problem was speech development, she first received speech therapy. Her parents then took full responsibility for her upbringing, including her social and academic growth. She attended Army Public School and College, PMA Kakul, till the eighth grade because of their active participation, which created a positive atmosphere. Her health suffered after a time of neglect brought on by familial circumstances. After a few years, when things in her family had calmed down, she went back to school and is now working for her matriculation at Allama Iqbal Open University (AIOU), which provides both private and online courses and certificates. She is content with her daily schedule and hopeful about the future.

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1.2 Research Questions

The study evaluated the following research questions:

- I. Does Miss Fatima flout the Maxim of Relevance during conversation?
- II. If so, what is the frequency or percentage of occurrence?
- III. Is Miss Fatima aware that her responses lack relevance?
- IV. If so, does she experience any discomfort due to this?

1.3 Objectives of the Study

This research aims to:

- I. Identify instances of flouting the Maxim of Relevance.
- II. Determine the frequency or percentage of such occurrences.
- III. Examine the patient's awareness of the relevance of her responses.
- IV. Assess her level of comfort in these interactions.

1.4 Significance of Study

This study can play an important role in the broader area of linguistic research by providing a case study of patient with Down syndrome. It can offer insights into the role of maxim of relevancy, its importance, and its effect. Through the analysis of the use of maxim of relevancy, we can get knowledge about the mental schemes retained by patient with such condition which can further give foundation to their treatments, working areas, their level of understanding and their emotional state and reaction. This can promote a deeper understanding of maxim of relevancy. The findings of this research can have suggestions for many speech pathologist and doctors who works for the treatments of patients with this condition. By understanding the role of maxim of relevancy in conversation with Down syndrome patients, doctors and families can develop more effective communion strategies. The study of analysis of maxim of relevancy in patient of Down syndrome holds significant role for many reasons. Generally, this analysis provides a precious opportunity to scrutinize the connection of patients, doctors, families, psychological factors and language.

1.5 Statement of Problem

Miss Fatima's conversational interactions may exhibit a pattern of flouting the Maxim of Relation (relevance), a core principle of cooperative communication. This research investigates the frequency of such instances, Miss Fatima's awareness of her responses' irrelevance, and her emotional response (specifically, discomfort) when she perceives this lack of relevance. Understanding these aspects will shed light on her communicative competence and the interplay between conversational awareness and emotional experience.

1.6 Limitations

Miss Fatima is the only case study, which restricts how broadly the results can be applied. The findings might not apply to other people with comparable communication styles. Miss Fatima's conversational behavior may be influenced by her awareness of being watched (if applicable), which could make her answers less or more pertinent than they would be in a natural situation. The relevancy of Miss Fatima's answers may vary depending on the particular conversational situations that were studied (subject, interlocutor, and setting). Different communication styles may be elicited by different settings. Her cognitive processing and, consequently, the significance of her answers, may be impacted by variables such as exhaustion, mood, or worry. It is challenging to properly account for or manage these internal states. This research is dependent on translated data. There may have been prejudice added and some distinction lost as a result of the translation process.

1.7 Delimitations

The study mostly ignores other Paul Grice maxims in favor of concentrating solely on the relevance maxim. Because there is only one participant in the study, the results cannot be generalized to a broader population. The findings only apply to the precise situations that the patient chooses for the conversation, which is required for manageability. The technique used to measure discomfort (such as self-reporting or observing nonverbal clues) will also be a boundary. The amount of data that may be gathered and examined may be constrained by the study's time and resource constraints.

This psycholinguistic analysis of maxim of relevancy in patient with Down syndrome has revealed their crucial role in discourse. By examining their usage, identification, and impact, the study has contributed to a deeper understanding of how language can promotes and bring forwards the views and thought processes of such patients.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section reviews existing research on psycholinguistics and Down syndrome, providing a foundation for exploring the use of the Maxim of Relevance. It will discuss the definition of psycholinguistics, examine the relationship between psycholinguistics and Down syndrome, and explore how a case study can be conducted in this context. Finally, this section will highlight previous research that has applied Gricean maxims to patients with similar conditions.

2.1. Psycholinguistics

Psycholinguistics is an interdisciplinary sub-field of study within Linguistics that concerns the scientific study of the relationship between human behavior and language. It belongs to the broader branch of science called Integrated Science. Psycholinguistics is the study of how humans produce and understand language (Warren, 2012). As an interdisciplinary field of study, its constituent disciplines include Linguistics, Psychology, and perhaps others. This term belongs mainly to the broader category called Language (PsychLing, 2023).

2.2. Down Syndrome

Down syndrome is the most common genetic cause of intellectual disability, occurring in approximately 1 in 700 live births (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2006). A genetic disorder known as Down syndrome is brought on by an atypical cell division that produces an additional whole or partial copy of chromosome 21. Down syndrome's physical characteristics and developmental abnormalities are brought on by this additional genetic material. The word "syndrome" describes a group of symptoms that frequently occur together. A syndrome is characterized by a pattern of abnormalities or issues. The illness bears the name of John Langdon Down, an English physician who was the first to describe it. The severity of Down syndrome differs from person to person. The disorder results in developmental delays and intellectual disabilities that lasts a lifetime. It is the most prevalent genetic chromosome that causes children to have intellectual impairments. Other illnesses, like as issues with the heart and digestive system, are also frequently brought on by it (Litin, 2018). Down syndrome can have modest to severe effects on one's physical and cognitive abilities. A small head, flattened face, short neck, low-set ears, up-slanted eyes, swollen tongue and lips, and a sloping under chin are some of the disorder's common physical symptoms. Poor muscle tone, aberrant dermal ridge patterns on the palms of the hands and soles of the feet, and heart or kidney abnormalities (or both) are possible additional symptoms of the illness. All individuals with Down syndrome experience intellectual disability, which typically varies from mild to substantial. Approximately 40 to 60 percent of individuals with Down syndrome have congenital heart disease. Increased knowledge of Down syndrome and early interventions can greatly improve the quality of life for children and adults with this condition and help them live fulfilling lives (The Editors of Encyclopedia Britannica, 2025).

2.3. Connection between Psycholinguistics and Down Syndrome

In children and adolescents with Down syndrome, shorter mean length of utterance (MLU), reading difficulties, and poorer language comprehension may all be linked to impaired phonological memory skills (assessed by non-word repetition) (Laws & Bishop, 2003). The majority of people with Down syndrome have mental retardation and speech and language impairments, especially in language production and syntax as well as poor speech intelligibility, although significant heterogeneity. The physical and cognitive characteristics of Down syndrome, as well as two communication-related domains—hearing and oral motor skills—are briefly described in this article before discussing study findings on the language and communication development of people with the condition. The development of language in Down syndrome is then discussed, with particular attention paid to communication behaviors during the pre-linguistic stage, language development in children and adolescents, and language development in adults and the aging stage. It outlines the four areas of language development—phonology, semantics, syntax, and pragmatics—in people with Down syndrome. Next, this study offers research directions and intervention techniques for people with Down syndrome (Roberts et al., 2007). Although there is individual variance, people with Down syndrome, the most prevalent genetic cause of intellectual disability, often have a consistent linguistic profile. With phonological and syntactic flaws, receptive language is typically stronger than expressive language. With an emphasis on phonology, vocabulary, syntax, and pragmatics, this review looks at their language and reading abilities. Common traits in hearing, oral-motor skills, cognition, social skills, and pre-linguistic/early nonverbal communication are first described. Lastly, it talks about future research directions and clinical consequences (Martin et al., 2009).

Relative strengths in visual skills and substantial deficiencies in auditory processing are typical characteristics of the Down syndrome (DS) phenotype, which has implications for language and communication. Whether this pattern describes the psycholinguistic profile of young adults with DS is unknown at this time. Fifty young adults with Down syndrome (DS) and fifty classmates with different intellectual disabilities were compared in the study. The findings indicated both deficiencies in visual psycholinguistic skills and more deficiencies in auditory psycholinguistic skills than in visual processing. Some auditory skills showed no discernible differences. This implies that DS's psycholinguistic pattern is not uniform, indicating the potential need for specialized educational assistance (López-Riobóo & Martínez-Castilla, 2019). Research on the linguistic development of people with Down syndrome from birth to maturity is reviewed in this chapter. It looks at the growth of speech, vocabulary, grammar, pragmatics, gestures and pre-linguistic communication, and outlines the relative advantages and disadvantages of each. Additionally, the chapter examines developmental paths, distinctions from other illnesses, and the impact of variables associated with Down syndrome, such as memory difficulties. The impact of social and linguistic settings is briefly discussed, with a primary focus on English language acquisition but, when feasible, consideration of other languages (Abbeduto et al., 2023). This qualitative case study examined the language abilities of a 19-year-old Down syndrome individual, focusing on psycholinguistic techniques. The study revealed cognitive processing, vocabulary, syntax, and phonological impairments, making it challenging to answer picture-based and multiple-choice questions. The study highlights the usefulness of psycholinguistic techniques in evaluating language abilities (Rosyidah, 2024).

2.4. Gricean maxims

Pragmatics is based on Grice's work on implicatures, or the discrepancy between what is meant and what is stated. According to his joint Principle, the principles of quality, quantity, relation, and manner govern communication, which is a joint activity. These maxims can be disregarded or broken because they are merely presumptions rather than rigid guidelines. Implicatures may result from obvious infractions when the listener presumes cooperation. A seemingly unrelated comment, for instance, may actually have a pertinent message. Grice found a number of patterns, including intentional flouting (e.g., irony, metaphor), violations resulting from maxim conflict (e.g., being truthful yet informative), and apparent but unreal breaches (e.g., stating the obvious). The fundamental Cooperative Principle and its tenets are probably universal for comprehending communicative purpose, even when particular implicatures differ among cultures (Kroeger, 2018).

2.5. Connection of Gricean Maxims and Psycholinguistics

The study examines the ways in which Grice's maxims support cooperative and mutual understanding of meaning. Grice's Cooperative Principle (quantity, quality, relation, and manner) encourages clear communication, but speakers occasionally purposefully disregard it, leaving out information to convey a hidden meaning, which can give rise to multiple interpretations and potentially distort the purpose of the communication. Cooperation is essential for meaningful conversation, emphasizing the importance of mutual understanding. The importance of this principle led to the development of pragmatics, which studies language use and context. The paper illustrates the ongoing central role of Grice's maxims in pragmatics and understanding meaning through a review of the literature (Goni et al., 2022).

Grice's maxims are helpful for comprehending normal discourse, but they are substantially different from the standards for therapeutic listening. Unlike ordinary conversationalists, therapists frequently anticipate hidden or suggested meanings. For instance, the therapist may interpret a client's statement "I am not angry" as metaphorical (flouting style), withholding information (flouting amount), hiding anger (flouting sincerity), or referring to someone else (flouting relevance). This discrepancy begs the following questions: Are Grice's maxims not as universal as people think? Is therapy flawed? Or can they be reconciled by recognizing the dual nature of therapy, with one level following Gricean maxims and the other following its own twisted logic? These disagreements draw attention to the incomplete knowledge of language use in treatment, even though the right viewpoint is still up for debate (Maier, 2024).

2.6. Connection between Gricean Maxims and Down Syndrome

In people with Down syndrome (DS), grammatical development is continuous but never fully developed. Growing utterance length, as indicated by mean length of utterance (MLU), is a sign of progress associated with chronological age (CA) (Rondal, 1995). Youngsters under five have trouble understanding hidden meanings and frequently take sentences at face value. Using a Truth Value Judgment test, this study investigated how children identify transgressions of the Maximize Presupposition principle and the Gricean maxims (Quantity, Relevance, Manner). Researchers tested adults, school-aged children, and toddlers and discovered a developmental pattern that was connected to age. All ages were better able to identify violations of Quantity and Relevance than of Manner and the Maximize Presupposition principle. According to the study, this discrepancy results from how each infraction affects the communication goals: listeners are less tolerant of unclear or pre-suppositional information (Manner, Maximize Presupposition) than they are of information that is mistaken or insufficient (Quantity, Relevance) (Panzeri & Foppolo, 2021).

2.7. Maxim of Relevancy and Patient with Down Syndrome

This study explores three key issues regarding language in adults with Down syndrome: First, the level of language proficiency they attain. Second, the continuation of language development, or aspects thereof, beyond adolescence, considering the idea of a critical period. Third, the impact of aging, including Alzheimer's disease, on their language abilities (Rondal, 1996). The study examines involvement and improvement in individuals with Down syndrome with the dancing practices as their rehabilitation process. Understanding how these individuals navigate Grice's Maxim of Relevance is crucial, as it directly impacts their ability to engage in reciprocal conversation, comprehend implied meanings and improvement of motor skills (Eshiev et al., 2024).

In psycholinguistics, many previous studies shows connection between Gricean maxims and patient with Down syndrome are important instruments that provides a rich and sophisticated dataset of complex concepts of this branch, as discussed in this chapter.

3. METHODOLOGY

In order to accurately fulfill the objectives of this research, this chapter discusses procedure of data collection and conclusion. The topics covered in this chapter are theoretical framework, research design, sample and procedure.

3.1. Theoretical framework:

Herbert Paul Grice made a significant contribution to the disciplines of linguistics and literary analysis with his pragmatic approach known as Gricean maxims. Four principles for successful communication are outlined in Grice's Cooperative Principle (1975): Manner (clarity), Relevance (pertinence), Quantity (informativeness), and Quality (truthfulness). In order to guarantee effective communication and produce implicatures (implied meanings), it is believed that participants in a conversation would adhere to these maxims. Cooperation between the speaker and the listener is emphasized by the cooperative principle. Speakers can purposefully disregard these maxims in order to transmit inferred meanings, depending on the listener to deduce the intended message, even if they are required to follow them. The foundation of Grice's theory of conversational implicature is this differentiation between spoken and inferred meaning. As Yule (1996) notes, this collaboration suggests that participants are typically not attempting to conceal, mislead, or deceive important facts. According to Mai (2009), the cooperation principle is crucial for effective communication. The maxims serve as a framework for creating and assessing persuasive discourse.

3.2. Research Design

Research design used for conducting this research is both qualitative and quantitative. The goal of qualitative research is to comprehend phenomena by using in-depth, narrative data. It investigates the "how" and "why" of human behavior and experiences through techniques including focus groups, observations, and interviews. The information gathered is not numerical and frequently takes the form of text, pictures, or videos. The goal of qualitative research is to comprehend the significance and background of events. It is a methodology that explores the subjective experiences and perceptions of individuals or groups. Qualitative research is an inquiry process of understanding based on distinct methodological traditions of inquiry that explore a social or human problem. However, research that uses quantitative methods is "a means for testing objective theories by examining the relationship among variables." According to Creswell's definition, quantitative research involves utilizing statistics and numerical data to determine

whether a theory regarding the relationships between things in the world is substantiated. It's a methodical process in which the researcher uses quantifiable data to examine particular hypotheses. Notably, throughout his numerous writings over the years, Creswell has improved his definition of quantitative research. Nonetheless, the fundamental components of evaluating theories and analyzing correlations between variables continue to be essential to his comprehension of this research methodology. (Creswell, 2014)

This research is a case study that is it involves an in-depth examination of a specific case or phenomenon to gain a comprehensive understanding of its characteristics and implications. This research approach will be utilized to analyze that what is Miss Fatima's compliance with Grice's Maxim of Relevance in discussion, analyzing how often she disregards it. It also investigates whether she feels uncomfortable answering questions that aren't pertinent to the situation.

3.3. Sample

The sample of this research is the translational transcript of the interview and conversation that was carried between researcher and Miss Fatima. This transcript was translated from the audio that was recorded during interview by researcher after Miss Fatima's consent and the audio serves as primary source of the data as it contains various sentences which will be analyzed for solving research questions.

3.4. Procedure

The research is based on deep textual, auditory and visual analysis of transcript and audios. Textual analysis employs techniques such as close reading, literary theory, discourse analysis, and content analysis to analyze the meaning, structure, and style of written or spoken language. This method is frequently applied to the analysis of texts, including speeches, poetry, and legal documents. Conversely, visual analysis is concerned with images, such as pictures, ads, movies, paintings, interviews and photos. It looks at the composition, meaning, and symbolism of visual aspects using techniques including semiotics, iconography, and formal analysis. This method is applied whether interpreting a commercial's message, deciphering a painting's meaning, examining a movie's use of color and composition or analyzing non-verbal cues or gestures. The term auditory analysis describes how the brain processes and interprets sounds. We can differentiate between various sounds, pinpoint their origins, and decipher their meaning thanks to this intricate process. This entails dissecting intricate sound waves into their constituent elements, including time, amplitude, and frequency, and then arranging them into coherent auditory events or objects. Speeches, audios, music, environmental sounds, auditory alerts are mostly analyzed with this type of analysis. The researcher will carefully review the transcripts and listen the audios multiple times to understand the content thoroughly. Researcher will carefully observe non-verbal cues and gestures of patient during interview and will note down any noticeable gesture or discomfort. This thorough analysis will help to identify answers to relevant questions. Once the violation or flouting of maxim of relevancy are identified, the researcher will delve into Gricean Maxim of cooperative principle to successfully fulfil objectives of the study.

This study carefully examined the text and recording of the interview involving Miss Fatima's responses using a qualitative and quantitative research design. By utilizing textual, auditory and visual analysis, the study recognized and investigated many violations of maxims of relevancy in the interview. The study explored flouting of maxim of relevancy, frequency of flouting and its impact on patient by utilizing Gricean Maxims of Cooperative principle. This analytical approach offers an all-encompassing framework for comprehending research questions.

4. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

This section explore the analysis of flouting of maxim of relevancy, frequency of flouting, impact on patient with realization. Flouting of maxim of relevancy in light of cooperative principle. By finding the flouting of maxim of relevancy, this research aims to shed light on impact on evoking emotions within patient.

4.1. Analysis

This study inspects a few flouting of maxim of relevancy within interview. These variations, occurs in accordance with cooperative principle that provided vision into how this flouting affect patient's emotional state. The case study of Miss Fatima proves that patient with condition of Down syndrome have potential to flout the maxim of relevancy during a conversation even if it is about their personal interest and is on their favorite topic. The frequency of flouting of this maxim reflects continuous flouting with different intervals within this interview. The non-literal expressions, which are frequently distinctive while expressing oneself, offered important insights into the tones of communication and the underlying ideas that are being articulated.

Different usage of sentences significantly impacted patient's emotional state. The level of comfort between interviewer and interviewee nurture a relationship of familiarity and shared understanding between the speaker and the listener. Resistant emotions like pity, confusion and comedy evoked, and this reflects how the hearer and speaker both views each other's points of minute comprehensiveness. It was analyzed that brief, memorable sentences are simpler to comprehend and are retained by speaker. Questions that were direct and short, were answered correctly and briefly by the patient, however questions with little bit complexity, even after explaining and cutting them short were not easily understood by patient and were answered with flouting of maxim of relevancy. One of the possible reason could also be her being little hesitant during the interview. Although it was clearly observed during the interview that she is not feeling anything going wrong when she was answering those questions where she was flouting with maxim of relevancy still her overall interview was in low voice and tone. Her continuous response was reflecting her level of familiarity and interest with the interviewer and her favorite topic still she was feeling shy to be recorded. For her comfort, video was not created so the entire interview was recorded and then it was transcribed.

4.2. Interview and its Analysis

Following questions/answers were held in the interview:

I. Who's your favorite actor, and what's the first thing you saw them in?

- a. Kamran Jelani, drama is Behroop

As, the question was direct and short, it was correctly answered by Miss Fatima, however in the second part of the question there was a little bit grammatical error, but still it conveyed the meaning and answered the question without flouting of maxim.

II. What do you like most about this actor's acting?

- b. Funny dialogues, he is angry, handsome

As the question was short but demanded a little bit more explanatory answer, Miss Fatima replied it in most concise manner by narrating three of her favorite things or qualities of her favorite actor. The answer was a collection of one simple sentence and qualitative words and conveyed the meaning resulting in relevancy in the answer.

III. If you met them, what would you ask?

- c. In how many dramas you do acting?

Again, the question was short and open ended, Miss Fatima replied it with her curiosity of asking her favorite actor about his dramas in which he is acting, due to her simple and direct response, it is difficult to know whether she wants to ask about a numerical figure or she just wants to know this so that she can watch all dramas of his favorite actor as her reply makes it difficult for us to understand the meaning of her response in deeper way. However her response on the surface level, clears out the answer of the question without flouting of the maxim of relevancy as she replied what she was asked for.

IV. What's your favorite movie or show they've done? Why?

- d. Behroop, because he is married, he lives with his brother.

This question was little bit complex for her, but was explained by interviewer. It can be analyzed with respect to two scenarios. If the answer is analyzed in a way that she answered by giving the reasons that were asked, so the flouting of maxim of relevancy is still not there as she have her own reasons and she provided us those. But if we analyze it in a way that questions the validity of the reasons she gave, so one of the flouting of maxim of relevancy would be that why would anybody like an actor on the basis of his marriage or living with brother, but again maybe she is having the scenario in her mind of his favorite actor in that drama fulfilling his duties with all morality in those roles of husband and brother and she is liking it.

V. Has this actor's work changed?

- e. At least he should do great acting in his other dramas

This question was close ended, Miss Fatima's response to this question holds flouting of maxim of relevancy, as she was expected to reply either yes or no as it was whether his acting skills and selection of roles got changed or not but she replied this with her opinion of him doing more great projects or acting, which can be a possible answer to the question of her suggesting something to her favorite actor.

VI. Do you like the roles they choose? Any roles you think they shouldn't have done?

- f. Yes, few, from beginning he is little bit angry.

This question has two parts, Miss Fatima answered the first one without flouting of maxim of relevancy by simply answering it as "Yes, few". In answer to her second part, she was expected to answer any character from actor's dramas which he should not have done but she replied about one of his acting skill of becoming angry which she didn't like, perhaps she was referring to his any role where he was angry and she don't want to see him in that way but she did not mentioned it as per requirement of the question which lead to the flouting of maxim of relevancy.

VII. What do you think what types of roles they shouldn't have done?

- g. Yes. He should not do planning against anyone.

This question demanded Miss Fatima's opinion about her favorite actor's roles which he shouldn't have done and she replied it with her perspective that he shouldn't have done roles in which he is planning against anybody. She still didn't took name of the character or role but it clarifies that what types of roles she don't want him to do so the answer to this question does not have any flouting of maxim of relevancy.

VIII. Besides acting, what else do you like (or not like) about them?

- h. Only acting

"Only acting" is the response to the query, "What else do you like (or not like) about them besides acting?" clearly contradicts the premise of the query, which is a flouting of the relevance maxim. The question specifically asks for information other than acting, yet the response only addresses it. As a result, the response does not supply the desired information and is therefore unrelated to the current discussion.

IX. How has their acting changed over time?

- i. Same, little bit change in other dramas.

When asked "How has their acting changed over time?" the response "Same, little bit change in other dramas" violates the principle of quantity rather than relevance. Although it is relevant to the subject (it concerns the actor's performing changes), the amount of information it offers is unhelpful.

X. Are there other actors you like in a similar way? How are they different?

- j. Change actor.

"Change actor" is the response to the query, "Are there other actors you like who are similar to you? What distinguishes them?" disregards the relevance maxim. The topic specifically requests a comparison and contrast between the actor that was first mentioned and other performers that are comparable to them. The "Change actor" suggests changing the subject totally, utterly disregarding this request. This solution violates the relevance maxim since it offers no details regarding comparable actors or how they differ, rendering

it unrelated to the main objective of the query.

XI. If you could put this actor in any movie role, what would it be?

k. Negative role, he should use good words with his other family.

Answer to this question also flouts the maxim of relevance as the question essentially asks about a hypothetical movie part, but it also accommodates personal choices. However, the response drops this imaginary setting and concentrates on the actor's actual actions and familial ties, which are quite distinct from the made-up situation. The reaction itself should be presented within the context of a movie role, not real-world behavior, even if the actor's personal life is the driving force for the view about a terrible portrayal. The response changes to include personal guidance.

XII. What do you think about how this actor talks about important issues?

l. In Drama Bakhtawar Rashid, did not thought, children will live without parents or not, I did not liked this thing.

Regarding the question "What do you think about how this actor talks about important issues?" the response "In Drama Bakhtawar Rashid, did not thought, children will live without parents or not, I did not liked this thing" violates the relevancy maxim. The inquiry concerns the actor's communication on significant matters. Although the response mentions a drama, it concentrates on a particular narrative point—that is, the character's (not the actor's) disregard for the children's future. This is a criticism of the character's behavior in a made-up story, not of the actor's portrayal of actual problems. The response is unrelated to the issue on the actor's own discourse on significant subjects since it confuses the actor with the role they play.

XIII. Has your opinion about this actor ever changed? Why?

m. No change, all I can say is that he should use proper words and should not go against anyone.

Has your view on this actor changed over time? The response to the question "No change, all I can say is that he should use proper words and should not go against anyone" stated as much. "Why?" disregards the relevance maxim. The initial question about whether their view has changed is addressed in the first section ("No change"), however the second section ("all I can say is that he should use proper words and should not go against anyone") switches the focus to suggestions for the actor's actions. *Why* the view changed (or, in this instance, *didn't* change) is the question. The "proper words" suggestion doesn't explain *why* the opinion didn't change. It is not an explanation of the stability; rather, it is a distinct commentary on the actor's behavior.

XIV. Do you think people give this actor too much or too little credit?

n. All I want is that acting should be good and should be complemented.

The response was "All I want is that acting should be good and should be complemented" to the query "Do you think people give this actor too much or too little credit?" disregards the relevance maxim. An assessment of how much credit the performer receives—too much or too little—is expressly requested in the question. The response entirely avoids addressing the central question of whether the existing level of credit is adequate, even though it does indicate a desire for good behavior and proper recognition. It is not a judgment on the particular actor's present degree of credit; rather, it is a statement on universal acting and appreciation principles. The response shifts the focus from the amount of credit to the acting's quality and the merits of commendation.

XV. What advice would you give this actor?

o. I want, whenever he does acting in dramas, he should use good words and should do good acting.

The response was "I want, whenever he does acting in dramas, he should use good words and should do good acting" to the query "What advice would you give this actor?" is *not* a disregard for applicability. Although it is fairly generic counsel, the response *does* offer guidance in response to the issue. The advice is nonetheless pertinent to the basic request of the question, while being a little tautological and lacking specifics. It doesn't supply facts unrelated to advising the actor or shift the topic. Although it can be viewed as uncooperative because it lacks meaningful or informative material, it does not violate the relevance rule.

XVI. Besides entertainment, do you think this actor's work is important in some way?

p. Only acting, only entertainment.

The response to "Only acting, only entertainment" for "Besides entertainment, do you think this actor's work is important in some way?" disregards relevancy. The question asks about significance *beyond* amusement, yet the response downplays its significance and ignores the main point of the question. It is irrelevant since it disregards other types of significance.

4.3. Flouting of the Maxim of Relevance: Self-Realization and Response

The findings of this research answer the research questions regarding the flouting of the Maxim of Relevance during conversation. It explores self-realization of the flouting and the response to it.

4.3.1. Does Miss Fatima flouts the Maxim Of relativity during conversation? If yes, with what percentage it occurred?

From the analysis the findings with respect to these questions are that out of 16 questions Miss Fatima responded nine answers with flouting, five answers without flouting of maxim of relevancy and two answers with partial relevancy and partial flouting. She flouted the maxim of relevancy with some intervals. However the questionnaire was designed with the combination of easy and difficult levels, it was easier for her to answer the simpler questions rather than difficult ones, and she was also very concise while answering the questions, her responses were not much explanatory. Following Table 1 and Figure 1 shows her flouting and cooperation with the maxim of relevancy.

Table 1: Statistics on Flouting the Maxim of Relevance in a Down Syndrome Patient's Interview About a Favorite Actor

Nature	Out of total 16 answers
Flouting of maxims	9 Answers
Cooperation with maxims	5 Answers
Cooperation and non-cooperation	2 Answers

Figure 1: Percentage of Maxim of Relevance Flouting in a Down Syndrome Patient's Interview About a Favorite Actor

Source: Author's work.

Figure 1 shows the percentages of flouting of maxim of relevancy that is 56%, presence of relevancy that is 31% and presence of partial flouted and partial cooperated answer as a mix category that is 13% in an interview of in total sixteen questions.

4.3.2. Was Miss Fatima realizing that she is answering without relevancy or not? If yes, was she feeling uncomfortable about that?

There may have been a discrepancy between Miss Fatima's answers and the questions asked during the interview. She doesn't, however, appear to have been aware of this lack of significance. It is therefore doubtful that she felt uneasy as a direct result of this apparent insignificance. Two more elements appear to have influenced her communication, even though she showed a willingness to participate in every question. First of all, the choice to record the interview on audio rather than video suggests that shyness probably played a part. This implies a desire for a format that is less visually demanding. Second, the low level of her voice suggests that she finds it difficult to express herself completely. Despite her apparent efforts to improve her communication skills, she struggled to turn her thoughts into coherent phrases and thorough responses. This implies that her comments were more difficult to formulate and deliver than it was to be aware of how divergent they were.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This section has presented comprehensive conclusion of the research based on the analysis of flouting of maxim of relevancy conveyed through the Cooperative principle and Maxims of Paul Grice in the patient with Down syndrome. This section concludes with the future recommendations for future researchers, urging further exploration of Gricean maxims, their flouting and their investigation with respect to psycholinguistics. The case study of Miss Fatima revealed a multitude of flouting of maxim of relevancy that offered insightful perspectives into the linguistic and communicative tones. The expressions were crucial in shaping the participants' perceptions and modeling the description. This can better hold the power of language usage and comprehensiveness for sake of understanding of parents or patient's close ones so that they can console, treat and understand the patient with different and easy communicative techniques.

5.1. Future Recommendations

The participant pool for future studies examining relevance in people with Down syndrome can be expanded to include larger and more varied samples, representing a range of ages, socioeconomic backgrounds, and language proficiency. To further understand the intricacies of relevancy creation and understanding, they can add qualitative techniques, such in-depth discourse analysis, to quantitative data. In order to comprehend how context affects performance, researchers might also concentrate on certain communication settings, such as interactions with peers or professionals. It is possible to use longitudinal studies to monitor the evolution of relevance skills over time and pinpoint critical intervention windows. Down syndrome-specific difficulties can be distinguished with the aid of comparison groups, such as those with various intellectual disabilities. A more comprehensive knowledge of conversational capacities can be obtained by analyzing multimodal communication, including non-verbal cues. Lastly, by emphasizing practical guidelines and practical application, researchers can create and assess focused interventions meant to enhance relevance skills.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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